

THEORETICAL PRINCIPLES OF USING ELECTRONIC DICTIONARIES IN TRANSLATING ENGLISH LANGUAGE MATERIALS INTO UZBEK

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Abstract. The article presents analysis and conclusions about the process of translation from English to Uzbek and the electronic dictionaries used in it, as well as methodological and theoretical aspects of the translation process.

Key words: English, Uzbek, simultaneous translation, mechanical translation, dictionary, electronic resources.

INTRODUCTION

Today, the interest of the young generation in learning foreign languages, especially English, is increasing. Therefore, in order to teach this language more deeply in all educational systems, pedagogues are required to make extensive use of innovative methods. and with the full understanding that learning the languages of culturally developed times is the main factor in acquiring the achievements of world science and development, the importance of language is definitely being paid attention to in choosing a profession even among high school students. Like other fields, language learning also depends on the age of the students along with their minds.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In order to know, analyze, study and apply the achievements of modern science, it is necessary to know the language of these technologies first.

Modern information and communication technologies (ICT) and Internet resources play an important role in finding a solution to these issues and problems. The issue of improving information technology and computer literacy of young people seems to be an easy situation nowadays, but the formation of theoretical knowledge, especially the skill of translating from English to Uzbek, is a particularly important aspect. Because the psychology of pupils and students has a special place in the direct implementation of the translation [1].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

First of all, electronic resources help to master the grammatical concepts and terms of the language faster. By studying the similarities and differences between languages and quickly analyzing them with modern tools, not only English but other languages are easy to learn. Comparison of language phenomena at the phonetic, lexical, and grammatical levels provides material

that enriches the field of linguistics. Therefore, cross-linguistic comparative analysis is important. This ensures not only the acquisition of new material in a foreign language, but also an approach to it with special interest among students. We know that it is necessary to be familiar with fundamental concepts and theoretical sources in mechanical and synchronous forms of translation. For this purpose, the use of not only written but also electronic dictionaries has become a new pineapple of translation.

Examples of such electronic dictionaries are www.lingualeo.ru and others. At the same time, each word in such a dictionary can be re-presented to the user many times, which means that when mastering it, the correct spelling of this word, the lexical pronunciation by the representatives of the language-speaking people are kept in mind.

Multilingual electronic dictionary, its types and possibilities. When researching the development of a platform for multilingual terminological dictionaries, it will be useful to study the experience of electronic dictionaries and platforms available today. In the 21st century, with the introduction of information technologies in the field of professional activity and education of people, electronic dictionaries became widespread. The history of creating electronic dictionaries goes back more than fifty years. One of the first lexicographic resources created on the basis of a computer (at that time, still an electronic calculator) was the Georgetown University dictionary, collected during the famous Georgetown experiment - Georgetown University Machine Translation Research and Language Project (1956). It was followed by Webster's 7th computer edition (1963), Random House Edition of the English Language, 1966, and electronic editions of the American Heritage Dictionary (American Heritage Dictionary, 1969). Among these, it would be appropriate to count computer versions of explanatory dictionaries in modern English, such as Longman (Longman Dictionary of Contemporary English, 1978), Harper Collins (Collins COBUILD English Dictionary, 1979) [2].

The following are examples of bilingual dictionaries used in general work [3].

1. Lingvo (versions X3, X5).
2. Multitran.
3. Polyglossum (versions 3.52, 3.72).
4. MultiLex 6 ("Compact" and "Deluxe" versions)

To date, the global database of google.com, as well as yandex.ru, ok.ru, and other social networks with a global audience, have dual dictionary platforms for

all languages. Among them are "Academic Press Dictionary of Science and Technology", "Online Accounting Dictionary", "Art Dictionary", "Banking and Finance Dictionary", "Law Dictionary", "Online Medical Dictionary Electronic dictionaries such as 'at' can be counted. The online table of D. I. Mendeleev, the pronunciation of chemical elements and their names in 7 languages, the "WebElements" dictionary should be highlighted as a multi-language translation electronic dictionary.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it can be said that the use of electronic dictionaries not only allows for efficient use of common time, but also helps to quickly and easily create a context in the translation process. Therefore, the use of electronic dictionaries in the process of translation from English to Uzbek is theoretically and practically important.

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